

An Energy-based Characterization on Kaolinitic Clay Calcination: Drop Calorimetry and Standard Heat of Reaction

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Abstract. This study introduces isothermal drop calorimetry as an enthalpy-based characterization for clay calcination in the cement industry. The standard heat of reaction of kaolinitic clay calcination was quantified at calcination temperatures between 600–1000 °C using a drop calorimeter. Notably, the endothermic standard heat of reaction varies with calcination temperatures, first increasing from 600 °C till the onset of metakaolin recrystallization at ca. 900 °C, before decreasing between 900–1000 °C. Complementary tests such as thermal gravimetry (TG), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and particle size distribution (PSD) were carried out on the raw and calcined clays, helping elucidate the cause of the varied standard heat of reaction. The results indicate that, besides kaolinite dehydroxylation, continuous mineralogical transformations take place in the metakaolin-based phase after complete dehydroxylation leading to an increase in the endothermic standard heat of reaction. Altogether, this research uncovers the complexity of reaction mechanisms for kaolinitic clay calcination and provides new thermodynamic data, laying the foundation for future process modeling and facilitating thermal energy management in clay calcination process.

Keywords: drop calorimetry; calcined clay; kaolinite dehydroxylation; standard heat of reaction.

1 Introduction

The cement industry faces strong pressure to reduce carbon emissions and conserve energy [1]. A promising strategy is to partially replace Portland cement clinker with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs). Among them, calcined kaolinitic clays (metakaolin-based phases) have attracted significant attention because of their high pozzolanic reactivity [2]. However, their performance was proved to be highly dependent on the clay's mineralogical structure and by the calcination temperature, especially for industrial kaolinitic clays [3].

Historically, kaolinitic clay calcination is framed in terms of two major reactions: (1) dehydroxylation (350–800 °C), which produces an amorphous metakaolin phase;

and (2) recrystallization (~ 1000 °C), where metakaolin transforms into spinel. Nevertheless, debate remains regarding whether intermediate mineral states exist between metakaolin and spinel [4, 5]. Once kaolinite becomes amorphous, standard crystal characterization such as X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) have limited ability to resolve subtle structural changes [6]. Conversely, ^{27}Al solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) has revealed transitions in the aluminum coordination – indicating the formation of new intermediate phases in kaolinitic clays calcined between complete dehydroxylation and incipient recrystallization [7].

The enthalpy of formation and specific heat of kaolinite and metakaolin was measured since the 20th century [8]. Their complete thermodynamic data are available in the handbook [9]; such data are essential for process modeling and estimation of fuel consumption for clay calcination processes. However, past studies treated the metakaolin phase as a single, unchanging substance, overlooking the possible subtle transitions at different calcination temperatures. In this light, calculations based on those data could contain systematic errors. Such errors could be enhanced due to the complexity in compositions of industrial clays, impacting the reliability of process models applied in the preliminary design or process control systems of calcined clay production. In other words, there is a clear need for complementary characterization methods that can provide accurate thermodynamic data for clays undergoing calcination.

Isothermal drop calorimetry offers a solution for this industrial need. It accurately measures the cumulative enthalpy increments of materials from room temperature to a designated high temperature, enabling enthalpy-based, in situ assessment of industrial calcination processes. Though drop calorimetry was applied in materials research fields [10], its utilization in the cement industry is rather limited, highlighting a research gap that warrants further exploration.

In this study, the standard heat of reaction of clay calcination was measured across a temperature range of 600–1000 °C by isothermal drop calorimetry, with emphasis on the interval between complete dehydroxylation and the onset of recrystallization (800–1000 °C for the tested clay). Complementary TG, DSC, and PSD tests were conducted to follow the evolution of calcined clays' chemical and physical properties as a function of calcination temperature. Finally, potential applications of drop calorimetry in the cement industry are discussed.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Raw Material

A ground natural clay (Kaolin A, Vicar SA, Valencia (Spain)) was used for the study. Table 1 shows the clay's chemical composition determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF). XRD and Rietveld analysis indicate that kaolinite (~ 84.1 wt%) is the dominant phase, with quartz (~ 10.5 wt%) as the primary impurity. Minor phases include mica (~ 3.0 wt%) and hematite (~ 0.5 wt%). PSD analysis shows that the median equivalent grain diameter of the raw clay is around 6.2 ± 0.3 μm .

Table 1. Chemical Composition of the raw clay characterized by XRF and LOI* (at 975°C).

	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	TiO ₂	MgO	P ₂ O ₅	LOI _{975°C}
%	50.94	34.44	0.73	0.51	0.26	0.15	0.11	0.06	12.42

* LOI: loss of ignition.

2.2 Drop Calorimetry for Clay Calcination

A two-step drop protocol was applied in the drop calorimetry measurements to quantify the standard heat of reaction ($\Delta_r H$, J/g). This parameter represents the ideal amount of heat needed to convert the initial clay into the calcination products (i.e., room-temperature calcined clay and gaseous product) through a calcination-cooling cycle. It can also be expressed as the enthalpy difference at room temperature between the raw clay and its calcined products by Eq. (1).

$$\Delta_r H = (1 - LOI) \times H_{cc}^{T_{room}} + LOI \times H_g^{T_{room}} - H_{rc}^{T_{room}} \quad (1)$$

where $H_{rc}^{T_{room}}$, $H_{cc}^{T_{room}}$, and $H_g^{T_{room}}$ (J/g) represent the enthalpies of raw clay, calcined clay, and gaseous product at room temperature (T_{room} , °C), respectively, and the LOI is the loss of ignition (wt%) at the corresponding calcination temperature.

Figure 1 illustrates the two-step drop protocol, which is detailed as follows.

Fig. 1. The two-step drop protocol.

Two drop experiments were carried out at each selected calcination temperature (T_{calc} , °C). In the first drop, raw clay pellets are introduced into the calorimeter stabilized at T_{calc} to measure the enthalpy increment, ΔH_{calc} (J/g). The latter represents the enthalpy change from room-temperature raw clay to the thermodynamic equilibrium state of calcined clay and gaseous product at T_{calc} . Next, the dropped sample is cooled down to room temperature and retrieved from the sample crucible. In the second drop, the retrieved samples are reintroduced into the calorimeter at the same calcination temperature to measure the enthalpy increment, ΔH_{cc} (J/g), which represents the enthalpy

change from room-temperature calcined clay to its thermodynamic equilibrium state at T_{calc} .

By assuming negligible irreversible thermal effects during the cooling process after the first drop and the subsequent reheating process in the second drop, ΔH_{cc} can effectively represent the heat released from the calcined clay during the cooling process after the first drop experiment. Besides, given the low CaO content (0.26 %), the gaseous product of the Kaolin A calcination was assumed to be pure water vapor. Thus, by incorporating the enthalpy change of water vapor (ΔH_g , J/g) from T_{calc} to T_{room} – derived from established thermodynamic database [11] – the total heat stored in the calcination products throughout calcination and cooling, $\Delta_r H$, is calculated by Eqs. (2), (3) and (4):

$$\Delta H_g = H_g^{T_{calc}} - H_g^{T_{room}} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta H_{cool} = (1 - LOI) \times \Delta H_{cc} + LOI \times \Delta H_g \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_r H = \Delta H_{calc} - \Delta H_{cool} \quad (4)$$

where $H_g^{T_{calc}}$ and $H_g^{T_{room}}$ (J/g) are the enthalpies of water vapor at designated calcination temperatures and room temperature, ΔH_{cool} (J/g) is the enthalpy change of calcination products in the cooling process.

A SETARAM MHTC96 drop calorimeter was used in this study. The calorimeter was calibrated by dropping pure alumina samples into an empty crucible at a given temperature. Each drop experiment involved 7–8 successive drops with varying sample masses (20–150 mg). The two-step drop protocol was applied at 600, 700, 800, 850, 900 and 1000 °C to assess the $\Delta_r H$ across various calcination temperatures. The uncertainty of the $\Delta_r H$ was calculated based on Student's t-distribution with a confidence level set at 95 % and combining the uncertainty of the calibration and the two clay sample drops.

2.3 Ex-situ Calcination and Complementary Characterizations

Ex-situ calcination was carried out with 50 g of raw Kaolin A placed in quartz crucibles, followed by calcination in muffle furnace in air for 1 h at 600, 700, 800, and 900 °C, covering the typical industrial clay calcination temperatures. After the calcination, the crucibles were removed from the furnace and left to cool on a refractory brick in air to room temperature.

To evaluate how closely the 50g-1h ex-situ calcined clays approached the thermodynamic equilibrium at each calcination temperature, ex-situ calcined samples were prepared with reduced mass (~5 g) and extended calcination time (3 h). These samples were calcined in platinum crucibles, then cooled to room temperature in desiccators.

Thermal gravimetry (TG) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests were conducted using a Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter®. Specifically, ca. 30 mg sample was placed in platinum crucibles and heated from 30 to 1075 °C at 20 K/min under a nitrogen atmosphere (20 ml/min). TG and DSC were applied on the raw clay to establish its dehydroxylation and recrystallization temperature profile. TG was applied on both 50g-1h and 5g-3h ex-situ calcined clays to assess their dehydroxylation extents.

PSD analyses of raw and 50g-1h ex-situ calcined clays were conducted using a Malvern PSD analyzer equipped with a Hydro 2000S wet sample dispersion unit, using deionized water as the dispersant. Samples were incrementally introduced into the dispersion until the desired obscuration level (~12 %) was reached. A refractive index of 0.01 was applied across all tests. Each sample dispersion was subjected to 4 min of sonication before the measurement to ensure homogeneity and mitigate aggregation.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Kaolin A: TG, DSC, Evolution of Dehydroxylation Extent and Particle Size with Calcination Temperature

Figure 2 shows the TG and DSC curves for the raw Kaolin A. Between 350 and 850 °C, the clay undergoes its main mass loss due to kaolinite dehydroxylation – also indicated by a prominent endothermic peak in the DSC curve. Between 850 and 950 °C, the dehydroxylation process is essentially complete, indicated by the plateau in the TG curve and absence of significant thermal events in the DSC curve. At ca. 1000 °C, a sharp exothermic peak emerges, reflecting the recrystallization of metakaolin into spinel.

Fig. 2. TG and DSC curves of raw Kaolin A.

Figure 3 shows the dehydroxylation extents of ex-situ calcined Kaolin A prepared by the two protocols. In both cases, dehydroxylation extents increase progressively between 600 and 900 °C. Nevertheless, a residual mass loss is still observed in the TG measurements for each ex-situ calcined sample, likely due to the smaller sample mass (~30 mg) and the higher maximum temperature (1075 °C) used in the TG protocol. Besides, the 50g-1h samples have lower dehydroxylation extents than the 5g-3h ones at each calcination temperature, thus, indicating that – in addition to the calcination temperature – reaction kinetics and vapor-diffusion constraints within the clay stack could impact the overall dehydroxylation extent.

Fig. 3. Dehydroxylation extent of ex-situ calcined Kaolin A.

As shown in Fig. 4, the ex-situ calcined Kaolin A exhibits an overall increase in particle size upon calcination at 600 °C. With further calcination temperature rise, D(10) and D(50) remain stable whereas D(90) increase steadily, indicating the formation of a coarse fraction caused by particle agglomeration [12]. By reducing the overall surface area, agglomeration lowers the system's surface free energy and therefore reduce $\Delta_r H$.

Fig. 4. D(10), D(50), D(90) of raw and 50g-1h ex-situ calcined Kaolin A.

3.2 Evolution of Standard Heat of Reaction with Calcination Temperature

Figure 5 depicts the measured $\Delta_r H$ profile for Kaolin A. The profile exhibits five regimes: (i) a moderate increase (~5 %) from 600 to 700 °C, (ii) a plateau between 700 and 800 °C, (iii) a sharper increase (~15 %) from 800 to 850 °C, (iv) a second plateau between 850 and 900 °C, and (v) a decline between 900 to 1000 °C.

In Fig. 5, the $\Delta_r H$ ranges from 740.6 to 917.4 J/g. Considering the kaolinite content in Kaolin A (84.1%), the $\Delta_r H$ of pure kaolinite dehydroxylation ranges from 880.6 to

1090.8 J/g depending on the calcination temperatures, where the calculated $\Delta_r H$ using thermodynamic data in handbook is 1024.7 J/g [9, 11]. The observed trend of $\Delta_r H$ confirms that the enthalpy gap between raw and calcined clay at room temperature varies substantially with calcination temperatures, indicating that clays calcined at different temperatures constitute thermodynamically – and hence structurally – distinct materials rather than a single, invariant product.

Fig. 5. Standard heat of reaction, $\Delta_r H$ vs. calcination temperature.

Between 600 and 700 °C, the increase in $\Delta_r H$ is caused by the increase in the dehydroxylation extent (92.6–97.0 %) seen from 600 to 700 °C in the ex-situ calcined clays. From 700 to 800 °C, the $\Delta_r H$ remains stable, which is parallel with the near-complete dehydroxylation observed in Fig. 3. A second surge is observed in the trend of $\Delta_r H$ between 800 and 900 °C. This increase cannot be explained by the evolution of dehydroxylation extent (98.6–98.9 %), which is stable in this temperature range. The increase of particle size also cannot explain this behavior as the contribution would be exothermic which is against the observations. In addition, no distinct peak is observed in the same temperature range of the DSC curve of raw Kaolin A.

Hence, it is reasonable to assume that the second boost of $\Delta_r H$ is caused by continuous transformations between 800 and 900 °C within the calcined clay, further consuming energy in ways that are not captured by a specific DSC peak. As stated in Section 1, the ^{27}Al solid-state NMR results implied the formation of intermediate phases in fully dehydroxylated and not recrystallized calcined kaolinitic clays [7]. The measured $\Delta_r H$ profile supports this view; however, to further investigate this intermediate transformation, advanced structural characterization, such as synchrotron X-ray and solid-state NMR, will be needed as they can provide direct structural information in poorly crystalline systems. Beyond 900 °C, the significant drop of $\Delta_r H$ is caused by recrystallization as the sharp exothermic peak observed in the DSC curve.

3.3 Application of Drop Calorimetry in Cement Industry

By leveraging drop calorimetry, a deep understanding of the reaction thermodynamics of kaolinitic clay calcination can have positive industrial implications for both thermal energy management and calcination temperature screening.

Fig. 6. ΔH_{calc} and ΔH_{cc} vs. calcination temperature.

Thermal energy management in industrial calcination and cooling processes: Figure 6 shows the profiles of the heat of calcination ΔH_{calc} and the heat of cooling ΔH_{cc} . As depicted in Fig. 1, ΔH_{calc} is the enthalpy difference between raw clay at T_{room} and calcined products at T_{calc} ; thus, it can represent the theoretical minimum heat consumption in the clay calcination (ΔH_{calc}^{min}). Besides, ΔH_{cc} is the enthalpy change of calcined clay from T_{room} to T_{calc} , representing the maximum energy recovery in the cooling process (ΔH_{cool}^{max}). Both terms grow along with the calcination temperature, i.e., ΔH_{calc} increases gradually from 600 to 800 °C and then accelerates between 800–850 °C, reflecting the additional thermal energy needed to drive the assumed continuous transformation in the calcined clay after complete dehydroxylation. Above 900 °C, ΔH_{calc} starts to decrease due to the exothermic recrystallization. In contrast, ΔH_{cc} increases uniformly from 600 to 1000 °C.

In industrial practice, these theoretical benchmarks, i.e., ΔH_{calc}^{min} and ΔH_{cool}^{max} , can facilitate both the design and operation of cement plants. They provide theoretical boundaries for the thermal energy input and potential heat recovery per ton of clay, guiding the design of calcined clay production lines. Besides, by comparing the actual energy consumption and recovery of operating cement plants with ΔH_{calc}^{min} and ΔH_{cool}^{max} , drop calorimetry provides a straightforward way to track the energy efficiency of the calcination and cooling processes.

Potential in screening clay calcination temperature: The two-step drop protocol extended the utility of drop calorimetry by measuring the ΔH of clay calcination – a metric that captures enthalpy changes among calcined clays produced at different calcination temperatures. For kaolinitic clay with high kaolinite content, the results show that

small temperature increments, particularly between 800 and 900 °C, can yield measurable differences in the Δ_rH , reflecting changes in the enthalpy of calcined product. This result indicates that calcined clays with higher enthalpy have potentially a more disordered structure – often correlated with higher pozzolanic reactivity. Hence, there is a potential to relate the Δ_rH to calcined clay reactivity metrics. Although the direct correlation between Δ_rH and pozzolanic reactivity is pending validation, the results suggest that isothermal drop calorimetry can sensitively distinguish the subtle difference between clays calcined at different temperatures and narrow down the most promising calcination temperatures.

4 Conclusion

Overall, this study introduces drop calorimetry as a thermal energy-based characterization for kaolinitic clay calcination. The results present standard heat of reaction of kaolinitic clay calcination at different temperatures, implying that subtle transformation happens in calcined clays between complete dehydroxylation and early recrystallization. Based on the results, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. Standard heat of reaction of kaolinite dehydroxylation: The standard heat of reaction of kaolinite dehydroxylation is not constant and is in range of 880.6 to 1090.8 J/g depending on the calcination temperature, which agrees with the calculated standard heat of reaction, 1024.7 J/g, based on thermodynamic data in handbook.

2. Subtle transformations beyond dehydroxylation: While the dehydroxylation of kaolinitic clay is essentially complete by ca. 800 °C, a second increase of the standard heat of reaction between 800 and 900 °C is observed which implies subtle structural transformations in the calcined clay. The smooth DSC curve at this temperature region indicates the continuous and low magnitude nature of the transformation.

3. Industrial application of drop calorimetry: The method can serve as an in-situ test to model the calcination and cooling process in cement industry, it provides key values such as minimum heat consumption in calcination and maximum heat recovery in cooling process, facilitating design and thermal energy management of cement plants. Besides, the method can distinguish subtle energy differences between clays calcined at different temperatures, narrowing down the optimal calcination temperature range.

As for future research prospects, complementary ongoing research will help to validate the correlation between the standard heat of reaction and established reactivity indices (e.g. R^3 reactivity test and 28-days compressive strength) and investigate the intermediate transformation between dehydroxylation and recrystallization using advanced structural characterizations, i.e., synchrotron X-ray and solid-state NMR. Moreover, the actual optimal end temperature in industrial processes may diverge from the thermodynamic “ideal” due to the limitation in heat transfer and heterogeneity of temperature distribution within large-scale equipment. Hence, a deeper understanding and modeling of the heat transfer and flow phenomena in industrial calcination is essential for translating laboratory-derived insights into practical, full-scale operations.

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